

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

No. 83 – June 2026 · <https://hab.ioc-unesco.org/>

Long and Winding Sea-lanes for Fish-Killing Algal Events

An ancient idiom “dead fish rot (or stink) from the head down” – possibly attributable to Turkish or Persian fishers but the origin is lost in the mists of time – is nowadays more frequently invoked as a metaphor for socio-political, scientific, military or corporate incompetence from the top administrative level (Fig. 1). The saying also applies to coastal zone resource management from a socio-economic perspective! But from a purely biological view this proverb is likely untrue; uncleaned healthy fish tend to decompose first from the internal organs, i.e. digestive tract (author: *pers. observations* of “guts” as a former professional quality grader for wild-caught Pacific salmon in British Columbia).

But what about wild or aquaculture fish killed by exposure to ichthyotoxic blooms, where the gills are often the proximal target organ by putative toxins, allelochemicals or hydromechanical damage? To our knowledge, there has been no concerted scientific effort to examine the fish *corpus delicti* to determine the time course of tissue decomposition after exposure to fish-killing algae. (A personal anecdote: the author consumed grilled wild Pacific salmon

freshly killed by a bloom of *Heterosigma akashiwo*. No known measurable biotoxins were found in the flesh. The human test subject survived with no ill effects, to tell the tale....). The question often arises as to whether freshly killed fish by non-toxicogenic algal blooms, or where known biotoxins in the flesh are below detection limits, are safe to eat. Human ethical concerns preclude such consumption trials and therefore the precautionary principle prevails. The fishers and aquaculture fish producers (and their sceptical insurers) consider such Agatha Christie detective inquiries as mere sophistry – fish killed by algal blooms cannot (legally) be marketed or consumed and hence lose all value. But now back to the fish-killing algal blooms.

There is a long and winding trajectory of studies leading from species composition and dynamics of fish-killing algal blooms to ichthyotoxic mechanisms causing mass fish mortalities and other ecosystem effects. Early impetus was provided by an International Workshop on Fish-killing Marine Algae (Oslo, Norway, 2011) hosted by the Norwegian Veterinary Institute as part of the pilot project “Algefisk” financed by the Research Council of Norway, and co-sponsored by the IOC-UNESCO Harmful Algal Bloom Programme (briefly noted in HAN 45 [1]). The technical workshop convened researchers on ichthyotoxic algae, fish pathologists, algal toxin chemists and aquaculture industry representatives to share experiences, ideas and approaches to addressing ichthyotoxic algal events. Frankly, we were inspired by describing the challenges but confronted with a massive deficit in knowledge and understanding about such events at the time. International attention on fish-killing microalgal blooms was next highlighted at the ICES-IOC WGHABD meeting in Oban (2012), and again in Belfast (2013) with establishment of a specific Term of Reference (ToR) on fish-killing algal

Fig. 1. Acknowledgement to the independent Scottish connoisseurs at Whiskey Moods for inspiration.

unesco

Intergovernmental
Oceanographic
Commission

Content

Featured article

Long and Winding Sea-lanes for Fish-Killing Algal Events
Allan Cembella 1

Blooms of ichthyotoxic species and Ciguatera

Unprecedented *Karenia cristata* bloom and catastrophic mass mortalities, shellfish toxicity and human respiratory problems in South Australia 6

Unprecedented *Fibrocapsa japonica* bloom in Southern Brittany (France) 8

First record of *Fukuyoa* sp. in Campeche, Mexico 10

Trophic interactions and ciguatera risk in a warming ocean 12

FAO-IOC-IAEA New Guidance for HAB and Toxins monitoring 13

Ciliate and Dinoflagellate Blooms in Contrasting Coastal Environments

Red and green waters and *Mesodinium* blooms in Southern Brittany (France) 14

Noctiluca scintillans blooms and *Strombidium* in the Gulf of Nicoya, Costa Rica 17

Forthcoming Events

XMAS 2027 in Xiamen, China 19

ICMSS in Exeter, UK, 6-11 September 2026 20

Networking and Coordination

DART, a regional effort against toxic diatoms 21

Fig. 2. Programme for the Advanced International Colloquium and Technical Workshop on fish killing marine algae and their effects.

blooms. The WG also decided to revise the classic but outdated Cooperative Research Report [2] on HAB effects on mariculture and marine fisheries published in 1992 for the ICES region. This influential but rather sparse document (only 38 pages) provided a cursory overview of HAB effects on living marine resources – primarily fish and shellfish. There were no documented distinctions of “fish-killing blooms” as a functional group, and little understanding of the proximal mechanisms of fish mortalities. From a monitoring and resource management perspective, resolving an apparently simplistic equation (harmful algal bloom = dead fish) was largely a struggle to identify the causative microalgal “species” and whether their unknown “ichthyotoxins” were the primary or exclusive lethal mechanism.

Aquaculture salmonids are the major finfish resource at HAB risk (ca. 95% by value) within the ICES region, comprising the North Atlantic including ocean gateways to the Arctic and Northern European marginal seas. Historical and prospective future losses are considered in a heavily capitalized industry with inconsistent reporting procedures

and inadequate risk assessment strategies. This salmonid risk situation due to HABs is replicated to a large extent in other economies (e.g., Chile, Pacific Northwest Canada and USA, Atlantic Canada, Tasmania, etc.) but does not fairly represent the global scenario for fish-killing blooms affecting other fish species and artisanal or small-scale fisheries.

Fig. 3. Invited speakers and hosts of the “Advanced International Colloquium and Technical Workshop on Fish-Killing HABs”. Puerto Varas, Chile October 8–11, 2019. Photo courtesy of Oscar Espinosa, IFOP.

Establishment of a Term of Reference (ToR) within the ICES WGHABD (Belfast 2013) to address fish-killing blooms and marine mortalities coincided with updates and refinements to HAEDAT reporting of such events. Subsequent development of the Harmful Algal Information System (HAIS) as a global resource is managed by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC), including HABMAP/OBIS (<https://obis.org/node/33dec23c-af65-4fb1-a437-79543c562ef0>). Globalization of the original ICES HAEDAT with records since 1985 for the North Atlantic region, has expanded as the revised ICES-PICES-IOC HAEDAT (<https://haedat.iode.org/>) and now provides a global template for entry of data on fish-killing and marine mortality events.

The IOC torch (*not the Olympic one*) on the fish-killing theme was carried from the ICES WGHABD and ignited at IOC-IPHAB XI (Paris, 2013) with the establishment of the Task Team on Fish Killing Marine Algae (Resolution XI.7). In subsequent intersessional periods the major tasks were primarily directed towards integrating descriptive data and developing knowledge on ichthyotoxic microalgae and their putative toxins, addressed by participation at conferences, project meetings and workshops to yield reports and primary publications. An international colloquium on the fish-killing algal theme was coordinated by IPHAB and GlobalHAB and co-sponsored by IOC, SCOR and the

Chilean government, through CORFO and cooperation of CREAN-IFOP (reported in HAN 63 [3]) (Fig. 2). The colloquium convenors invited international experts to Puerto Varas, Chile in 2019 to review disciplinary knowledge on all aspects of fish-killing algae and associated mortality events (Fig. 3). A public forum opened the discussion to local socio-economic stakeholders from the fish aquaculture industry and resource management agencies to address the critical problem and to propose future monitoring and mitigation strategies.

After a long gestation the workshop report yielded the influential GlobalHAB white paper on fish-killing marine algae [4] (Fig. 4). This state-of-knowledge review of causative organisms, ichthyotoxic mechanisms, impacts and mitigation strategies identified current gaps for future research on all aspects of fish-killing algal blooms. The document was also intended to provide guidance for socio-economic stakeholders such as fishers, aquaculture operators, and associated insurance brokers for risk assessment and improved management of the consequences of fish-killing HAB events.

A major leap forward in our international organizational strategies to address the fish-killing algal theme was provided by the recent affiliation of IOC-IPHAB with the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) at the inaugural session at FAO, Rome, 2023 (IOC-FAO/IPHAB XVI). This coincided with the publication of the FAO, IOC and IAEA joint technical guidance for the implementation of early warning systems for harmful algal blooms [5]. Fruitful interactions by the IPHAB fish-killing algae task team on the development of EWS contributed Chapter 5 on high biomass blooms causing fish kills and other environmental impacts, describing remote sensing and EWS management strategies specifically adapted to fish aquaculture.

A recent effort coordinated by FAO via IPHAB Task Teams for assimilation of existing global HAB data to produce web-based interactive HAB Risk Maps based on the Google Earth platform has selected fish-killing algal blooms and events as the pilot project (<https://dev.habs.earthmap.org/>) for development of EWS. For the fish-killing theme, affiliation with FAO has shifted focus

towards more research on seafood security and sustainable management of fisheries and aquaculture resources and HAB risk assessment. This has enhanced the IOC perspective to define the causative organisms, bloom dynamics, and toxigenicity, and the ecological nature of ichthyotoxic events. Accordingly, the IPHAB “fish-killing algae” theme has a revised mandate as the Task Team on Fish Killing Microalgae and Ecosystem Effects (FKAMEE) (Decision IPHAB-XVII.8) (<https://hab.ioc-unesco.org/iphab-task-team-on-harmful-algae-and-fish-kills/>) led by Co-Chairs Allan Cembella (Germany), with a focus on basic marine science research, and Kazumi Wakita (IOC/WESTPAC-HAB), representing the socio-economic and human social dimension.

Notable revisions to the TT include: i) increased focus on HAB early warning systems (EWS), and monitoring, forecasting and mitigation strategies, specially designed for fish aquaculture; ii) inclusion of cyanobacteria and freshwater/brackish microeukaryotes (e.g. *Prymnesium parvum*) with inimical effects on fish health and survival in coastal zones; iii) integration and mod-

elling of multi-factorial environmental and anthropogenic stressors, e.g., disease and pathologies, and other biotic factors, which may synergistically contribute to sub-lethal fish morbidity and mortalities. The FKAMEE TT collaborates closely by co-membership on other IPHAB TTs: e.g., on Communications, EWS, HAEDAT-HAIS, Taxonomy, Biotoxins, in particular. For example, the FKAMEE TT provides guidance to the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae (<https://www.marinespecies.org/hab/>) (are *Phaeocystis* and *Noctiluca* ichthyotoxic?) and to the IOC-UNESCO Toxins database (<https://toxins.hais.ioc-unesco.org/>) (What are the true ichthyotoxins? What about these weird undefined allelochemicals, sterolysins and membrane-disruptive ROS compounds?). Although >120 eukaryotic microalgal and cyanobacterial species have been reported as “fish-killing algae” usually from dense high-magnitude blooms, the lethality mechanisms are typically unclear and undefined.

Rapid progress on the development of the IOC-UNESCO Toxins database can be best illustrated as follows: 87 biotox-

Fig. 4. IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB white paper on fish-killing marine algae — causative organisms, ichthyotoxic mechanisms, impacts and mitigation strategies.

ins were added during the IPHAB XVII Intersessional (2025-2026), but the total meagre reported ichthyotoxins score (by March 2025) (zero goniodomins, zero prymnesins, one karlotoxin [sterolysin]) has increased dramatically (by February 2026): seven goniodomins, four prymnesins, one karlotoxin, and more sterolysins (e.g., leadbeaterins) are expected soon.

The IOC-FAO IPHAB and subsidiary regional groups (IOC/IOCARIBE-ANCA, IOC/WESTPAC-HAB, IOCAFRICA/HAB, FANSA, ANCA) together with associated international bodies (ICES, PICES and their Working Groups) have played a critical role in knowledge acquisition and scientific development studies on fish-killing algal bloom events for more than two decades. The IOC-SCOR Global-HAB programme leads the HAB science agenda on this theme. Collectively these organisations have convened, sponsored or co-hosted literally dozens of symposia, meetings, webinars, discussion groups, training workshops and courses, and Special Sessions at national and international conferences. Major programme presentations and special sessions on Fish Killing Algae and Ichthyotoxins have been featured, at least since the ICHA15 meeting (Korea, 2012) and at each successive international conference until ICHA21 (Punta Arenas, Chile, 2025). Presentations on combining meta-Omics approaches for ichthyotoxic HABs demonstrated for the first time the functional interactions of ichthyotoxic species in plankton communities and the (“toxic”) mechanisms of collateral damage to fish and other marine fauna (ICHA21 conference highlights from HAN81 [6]). Functional models of toxigenicity of groups of putative ichthyotoxins, such as sterolysins, are now applied to explore their membrane-disruptive effects on fish gills and plankton predators and competitors. In contrast to the quasi-predictable HAB events linked to shellfish toxins in many global coastal regions, mass fish-killing bloom events appear to defy forecasting and predictions based on current knowledge and paradigms of oceanographic and ecological theory. Recent apparently stochastic fish events would include the sudden devastating salmon mortality event in northern Norway (2019) caused by *Chrysochromulina leadbeateri* after decades of few fish-

Tonnes of fish found dead in German-Polish river

Fig. 5. Reported mass fish mortalities caused by a *Prymnesium parvum* bloom in the Oder River basin between Germany and Poland (BBC News International, 2022).

killing events caused by haptophytes of any *Chrysochromulina* or *Prymnesium* species. But *C. leadbeateri* blooms recurred in 2025 albeit with lesser fish-killing consequences. A sudden massive ichthyotoxic bloom of *Prymnesium parvum* in the Oder river basin shared by Poland and Germany in 2022 caused millions of freshwater fish deaths (Fig. 5). Since then, annual *P. parvum* occurrences are endemic to the region but have caused only minor fish mortalities. A large geographical scale and persistent bloom of *Karenia cristata* along the South Australia coast initiated in 2025 caused mass mortalities of marine life and respiratory irritation in humans (HAN 83 [7]). This species has been found previously off Newfoundland in Atlantic Canada and South Africa but never associated with harmful events. Discovery of brevetoxins in isolates from this extensive bloom were suspected to account for both human and environmental effects, but apparently the ichthyotoxic potential by *K. cristata* is orders of magnitude higher than can be explained by its brevetoxin content. This underscores the critical importance of defining true ichthyotoxins that may be distinct from known biotoxins. Are fish-killing blooms becoming more

toxigenic? Are they shifting their chemical ecological strategies in response to environmental changes? Or are we merely mis-characterising the fish-killing chemical agents in an ecological context? In any case, the fish-killing algae problem will not go away – indeed it continues to inspire and require further research because most fundamental questions are unresolved, and solutions for monitoring, mitigation, control are elusive. Meanwhile global demand for safe and secure seafood is increasing the pressure on declining wild fish stocks, and the growing dependency on aquaculture fish. More seafood resources are thereby at risk from targeted sub-mesoscale fish-killing blooms. Primary scientific research has yielded substantial knowledge dividends in the last decade – we are beyond the naive questions (*who killed the fish? How many? How fast did they die?*). But what is the outcome of all this research effort? We now know the structure and mode of action of a handful of true ichthyotoxins, e.g. a few sterolysins [8–9], and even a plausible scenario on how ichthyotoxic blooms may function in ecological interactions in the case of the *Chrysochromulina* bloom in northern Norway [10]. Conceptual fish-based models

(admittedly controversial) explain how toxigenic blooms may directly kill fish in aquaculture operations [e.g., 11]. Access to comprehensive time-series databases on HAB events (HAEDAT, HAIS/OBIS) has allowed for interpretation of fish-killing events over decades on a regional geographical basis, e.g. for East Asia [12] and the North Atlantic margin and Northern European seas [13, 14]. Nevertheless, there is increased appreciation that HABs are not always the sole or major cause of mass fish mortalities even in cases where putative fish-killing algal species may be present. In Chile most mass or enhanced salmonid loss events are indeed caused by HABs, whereas in Norway and the UK most losses are due to fish-gill diseases or parasites. In Atlantic Canada the highest salmonid mortality ever recorded was associated with sudden ocean temperature anomalies.

Perhaps surprisingly, the GHSR global data analysis [15] did not confirm the subjective impression created among the HAB research community and the general public that HABs have increased in magnitude and frequency on a global scale over the past four decades. The conclusion that “the intensity and frequency of specific blooms vary at regional and local scale, with increasing or decreasing trends and sudden occasional outbursts, but with *no uniform global trend* that can be discerned from that of increased observational efforts” applies even more to fish-killing events which are more sporadic and lack reliable time-series data. But not lumping all fish-killing events as mass mortalities with equal weight can yield a different conclusion. A global analysis of trends in fish mortality events showed that in particular for salmon production in Norway, Canada, and the UK, mass mortality events have increased in frequency from 2012 to 2022 [16]. Considering only the major loss events, the upper boundary of how many fish were killed in a specific mortality event has indeed increased over time.

The saga continues but we have made enormous scientific progress in the last decade, and the knowledge and strategies are ripe for rapid implementation. This perspective is the story of how coordinated multi-national and global networking has assisted in ‘top down’ coordinating research activities

and refining monitoring and mitigation activities, including in few limited circumstance control strategies to minimize harm to fish health and survival. Which proves the hypothesis - the dead fish caused by HABs are not “rotting from the head down” at least from the scientific research and management perspective.

Acknowledgements

Allan Cembella (Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Bremerhaven, Germany) prepared this article on behalf of the IOC-FAO IPHAB Task Team on Fish Killing Microalgae and Ecosystem Effects (FKA-MEE) and the ICES-IOC WG on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics (WGHABD). Insights, inspiration and contributions of individual members and associated scientists are much appreciated and acknowledged – in particular thanks to Gustaf Hallegraeff, Shauna Murray, Kazumi Wakita, Oscar Espinosa, Lars Johan Nausvoll, Justyna Kobos, Bengt Karlson, Cynthia Mackenzie, Philipp Hess, Uwe John, Beatriz Reguera, and Henrik Enevoldsen, but statements herein do not necessarily represent a consensus view of participants or their respective organizations.

References

1. GEOHAB 2012. Framework activities. International Workshop on Fish-killing Marine Algae. In Wyatt T (Ed) HAN 45, UNESCO, pp. 23. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000220399>
2. ICES 1992. Effects of harmful algal blooms on mariculture and marine fisheries, ICES Cooperative Research Report 181. 38 pp.
3. Guzmán L & Hallegraeff GM 2019. New Initiative on Fish-Killing Algal Blooms. In Reguera B & Mertens K (Eds) HAN 63, UNESCO, p. 2. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5109802>
4. GlobalHAB. 2023. Fish-Killing Marine Algal Blooms: Causative Organisms, Ichthyotoxic Mechanisms, Impacts and Mitigation. Hallegraeff GM(Ed) Paris, UNESCO-IOC/SCOR, 96pp. (IOC Manuals and Guides, 93 <http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-1964>
5. FAO, IOC & IAEA 2023. Joint technical guidance for the implementation of early warning systems for harmful algal blooms. Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper. 690. Rome FAO. 224 pp. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc4794en>
6. Murray S et al. 2025. ICHA 2025. Scientific Highlights. In Reguera B & Mertens

K (Eds) HAN 81, UNESCO, pp. 6–11. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17976905>

7. Hallegraeff GM et al. 2026. Catastrophic marine mass mortalities, shellfish toxicity and human respiratory problems from a *Karenia cristata* dinoflagellate bloom in South Australia, 2025. In Reguera B & Mertens KN (Eds) HAN 83, UNESCO, pp. 6–7. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20583164>
8. Place AR et al. 2024. *Sci Rep* 14:17998. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-68669-0>
9. Wang X et al. 2024. *Harmful Algae* 137:102681. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2024.102681>
10. Otte A et al. 2025. *Sci Adv* 11(26):eadv3390. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adv3390>
11. Mardones JI et al. 2021. *STOTEN* 766:144383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144383>
12. Sakamoto S et al. 2021. *Harmful Algae* 102:101787. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2020.101787>
13. Karlson B et al. 2021. *Harmful Algae* 102:101989. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2021.101989>
14. Bresnan E et al. 2021. *Harmful Algae* 102:101976. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2021.101976>
15. Hallegraeff GM et al. 2021. Global HAB Status Report. A Scientific Summary for Policy Makers. Hallegraeff GM et al. (Eds). Paris, UNESCO. (IOC Information Document 1399.)
16. Singh GG et al. 2024. *Sci Rep* 14:3763. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-54033-9>

Author

Allan Cembella, Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Bremerhaven, Germany

Email corresponding author:
Allan.Cembella@awi.de

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20583115>

Allan Cembella. Photo Merian Greenland